

Research

Experiments And Simulations of Drilling Titanium Alloy with Varying Process Parameters

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Abstract: Machining is an important material removal manufacturing process. Drilling is a kind of machining operation where a multipoint cutting tool is utilized to make holes in the workpiece. There is still an absence of research to understand the procedure of titanium alloy drilling completely. A 3D FEM model of drilling titanium alloys is developed to review the influence of cutting parameters on thrust force and torque. Simulations are done under different Spindle Speeds and feed to analyze the result of drilling parameters on machining performance. Experiments are performed to approve the outcomes from simulations.

Keywords: Cutting forces, Drilling, Finite element analysis, Titanium alloy.

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1. Introduction

Machining is one of the foremost broadly used manufacturing Processes. The structure of the object is transformed by eliminating material in the form of chips in machining operations. There are numerous kinds of machining; turning, drilling, milling, grinding, sawing and facing, etc. Drilling is a kind of machining procedure where a multipoint cutting tool is used to drill a hole in the workpiece. Drilling comes up with 40% to 60% of the entire material removal process during machining. Thousands of holes are drilled in the manufacture of an automobile, and a hundred thousand holes are drilled in the manufacture of an aircraft. Holes in metal structures are unavoidable and are the weakest part of the structure. Some of the common problems encountered in drilling are unnecessary forces that reduced drill life, drill fracture, burr formation in metals and delimitation in fiber-reinforced composites, drill wander, and vibrations that affect the surface finish and dimensional accuracy.

The literature on metal cutting was a mostly numerical and analytical model in the past. The early force models developed for the metal cutting process were purely empirical. [1, 2] published early literature on the machining of metals and developed early drilling models. As the understanding of the mechanics of metal-cutting processes improved, analytical models were formulated for the cutting forces [3, 4]. Recent developments in drilling models have

utilized either a mechanistic or finite element approach. [5, 6] have developed mechanistic drilling models. Separate models were developed for the cutting lips, and the chisel edge and a calibration procedure were proposed to determine all the model coefficients from drilling tests. The chisel edge and cutting lips models were experimentally validated for a wide range of machining conditions. This approach is based on the geometry of the process and relates the force to the chip area or chip load through the specific cutting forces. The specific cutting forces are empirically associated with fundamental machining parameters, and the model coefficients are determined from calibration experiments. [7] "has developed the approach of dividing conventional twist drill into a series of elementary cutting sections and applying the oblique cutting model for each elementary cutting section to predict the forces and torque in drilling."

Drilling of titanium and its alloys has been utilized in different industries, but the number of published research literature is very scarce. The complicated geometry of the drill, material deformation, and chip formation is the reason why it is technically difficult to model the drilling process. "To achieve the cost-effective machining of Ti, a better understanding of the underlying mechanism through better modeling is necessary" [8]. "The productivity gain in the drilling of titanium alloys lacks due to its low thermal conductivity and the subsequent high temperature and wear of the drill" [9]. The cutting tool industries have advanced significantly in the past decade. Improved cutting tool geometries and tool materials are available. This development results in the high-throughput drilling of titanium alloys at rates previously unachieved. [10, 11] "Studied the characterization of cutting forces in dry machining of titanium alloys and reported that the cutting forces increase with the increase in feed and increases in depth of cut."

The knowledge about Finite Element Model of metal drilling process in literature is very limited. "The first finite element modeling of machining was published by Klamecki [12]. Benefiting from advancement of computational power, finite element modeling (FEM) is becoming a standard, commercially-available tool to analyze the machining process in recent years. [7] "developed the approach of dividing a single cutting edge into a series of elementary cutting sections to predict the thrust forces and torque in drilling." [13] "developed a 3D FEM for the simulation of drilling burr formation process on the 304l stainless steel workpiece." [14] "simulated 3D drilling of Ti6Al4V using conventional twist drill." Isbilir and Elashah [15] "carried out the finite element analysis of drilling of titanium alloy, which provides a reasonable estimation of thrust force." This model can simulate the formation of continuous or discontinuous chips during the cutting process that depends on the cutting conditions. [16] "presented finite element modeling of drilling process using DEFORM." [17] "presented a 3D thermo-mechanically coupled finite element model of drilling process of steel 2080 using DEFORM, where the author concluded that thrust force and torque increase with increasing cutting speed and feed rate."

2. Finite Element Method Modeling

A 3D FEM model is developed that aims to simulate the drilling process, to calculate the cutting forces and torque in the workpiece throughout the drilling process. The FEM model is based on the Lagrangian formulation. "Because of the absence of an adequate number of opportunities in the past as well as complicated drill-workpiece interaction, most of the drilling simulation was performed with a particular level of simplification such as reducing the three-dimensional problem to a two-dimensional formulation" [18], "By assuming the cutting lips as a combination of small elementary cutting tools performing an orthogonal cutting operation" [19]. The current model has numerous advantages contrasted with the recently created 2D and simplified 3D models. It permits us to examine the tool-workpiece connection utilizing the full geometry of a twist drill bit.

2.1. Tool and Workpiece Model

For drilling of Titanium Alloy at dry cutting conditions, using of High-Speed Steel (HSS) tools with lower feed was recommended for better hole quality. A 3D FEM twist drill model was created, meshed, and assumed to be rigid. Cobalt

uncoated carbide was selected as a tool material. Geometric parameters of the drill bit are as follows: drill diameter of 10 mm, web thickness of 1.1 mm, helix angle of 21°, and point angle of 118°.

In the present FEM simulation of drilling, a deformable plastic-type workpiece is created as a cylinder type with a diameter 14mm and height 5mm. The drill and workpiece are divided into 20,000 and 25,000 grids, respectively. An adjustable meshing of the workpiece was performed with fine mesh close to the cutting lips. The drill bit and workpiece meshed with 4-nodes tetrahedral elements mentioned in (Figure 1a). The formation of chip that resulted from remeshing in showing in (Figure 1b). (Table 1) shows the details of variables for drilling; these include the Spindle speed and feed.

Table 1: Cutting parameters and their respective values

Parameters	Magnitude
Spindle Speed (rpm)	319, 638, 957
Feed (mm/rev)	0.06, 0.04, 0.02

2.2. Material Model

In this model, High-Speed Steel (HSS) is selected as the material of drill, and Ti-6Al-4V is selected as the material of the workpiece. Cutting deformed processes of material were usually recognized as plastic strain. Johnson-cook constitutive model was used for the flow stress model of cutting simulation, as follows in Equation (1)

$$\sigma = (A + B\varepsilon^n) \left(1 + C \ln \frac{\dot{\varepsilon}}{\dot{\varepsilon}_0} \right) \left[1 - \left(\frac{T - T_r}{T_m - T_r} \right)^m \right] \tag{1}$$

Where ε is the plastic strain, $\dot{\varepsilon}$ is the strain rate (s^{-1}), $\dot{\varepsilon}_0$ is the reference plastic strain rate (s^{-1}), T is the temperature of the workpiece (°C), T_m is the melting temperature of the workpiece (°C), T_r is the room temperature (°C). Coefficient A is the yield strength (MPa), B is the hardening modulus (MPa), C is the strain rate sensitivity coefficient, n is the hardening coefficient, and m is the thermal softening coefficient. The Johnson-Cook parameter values of Ti-6Al-4V are presented in (Table 2), [20].

Table 2: The Johnson-Cook parameter values of Ti-6Al-4V Alloy

A (MPa)	B (MPa)	C	N	M
782.7	498.4	0.028	0.28	1

Figure 1: (a) Drill bit and workpiece meshing (b) Formation of chip developed in FEM Model

2.3. Simulation Conditions

The workpiece is fixed in all directions in the present FEM simulation. The drill moves around Z-axis and goes down along the Z-axis at the same time. The initial temperature is 20°C and the convection heat transfer coefficient of the environment is 0.02 N/sec/mm/°C. A constant shear stress model is used, the friction factor is set 0.6, and a total of 9 simulations were performed

3. Experimental Setup

High-speed 5-axis CNC milling machine TH5660A performed experiments. The workpiece is mounted on the Kistler force dynamometer and holds the drill bit inside the chuck of the lathe. Machining is performed using the same variables mentioned in (Table 1). The work holding fixture is shown in (Figure 2a). A fixed-plate dynamometer was used to record the components of the cutting forces shown in (Figure 2b). The dynamometer data was passed through an amplifier and centralized on a computer using the DynoWare-Data Acquisition software, shown in (Figure 2c)

(a)

(b)

(c)

Figure 2: (a) Work holding fixture (b) Fixed-plate dynamometer (c) Data Acquisition Setup

4. Result and discussion

4.1. Impact of Drilling Parameters on Drilling Force

Drilling force regulates the power expense of drilling and also directly affects the cutting heat generated during the drilling process. (Figure 3) shows axial force (Z load) varies with time under different feed, and here spindle speed (319 rpm) is constant. (Figure 4) shows axial force (Z load) varies with time under different spindle speeds, and here (feed = 0.06 mm/rev) is constant. From the figure, it can be seen that the drilling force increases when the drill cuts into Ti-6Al-4V alloy and then reaches a steady value. Then, it varies in a certain range.

Figure 3: Axial force varies with time under various feed (Constant Spindle Speed = 319 rpm)

Figure 4: (a) Spindle Speed = 319 rpm, (b) Spindle Speed = 638 rpm, (c) Spindle Speed = 957 rpm, Axial force varies with time under various Spindle Speed (Constant feed=0.06mm/rev)

Simulation and experimental results of thrust forces for various spindle speed and feed are presented in Figure 5a) and Figure 5b) respectively. A constant decrease is visible in the thrust force as the spindle speed increase from 319 rpm to 957 rpm. From the figure, the influence of feed is more prominent than the spindle speed on the thrust force. The maximum rise in thrust force rises by more than was 10%, 15%, and 25% when the feed was increased from 0.02 to 0.04 mm/rev, 0.04 to 0.06 mm/rev, and 0.02 to 0.06 mm/rev respectively. Figure 5a) and Figure 5b) show that the simulation results and Experimental results are almost the same.

Figure 5: (a) Simulation results: Effect of Spindle Speed (rpm) and Feed (mm/rev) on Thrust force
 (b) Experimental Results: Effect of Spindle Speed (rpm) and Feed (mm/rev) on Thrust force

4.2. Impact of Drilling Parameters on Torque

For drill design, a significant parameter is drilling torque. Extreme torque will assist in the fracture of a drill. Figure 6 shows, the torque varies with time under various feed, and here Spindle Speed (319 rpm) is constant. Figure 7 shows torque varies with time under various spindle speeds, and here feed (0.06 mm/rev) is constant.

Figure 6: Torque varies with time under various feed (a) Feed = 0.02, (b) Feed = 0.04, (c) Feed= 0.06, and (Constant Spindle Speed = 319 rpm)

Figure 7: Torque varies with time under various Spindle Speed (a) Spindle Speed = 319 rpm, (b) Spindle Speed = 638 rpm, (c) Spindle Speed = 957 rpm, and (Constant feed=0.06mm/rev)

Simulation and experimental results of torque for various spindle speed and feed are presented in Figure 8a) and Figure 8b) respectively. Figure 8a) showed the results of changing the spindle speed and feed on the torque inside the drill body. The value of torque increases with the increase of Spindle Speed and feed but, in some cases, not uniform. The experimental results are displayed in Figure 8b). The same tendency is noticed in Figures 8a) and Figure 8b) that the simulation results and experimental results are almost the same.

Figure 8: (a) Simulation results: Effect of Spindle speed(rpm) and feed(mm/rev) on Torque(N-m) and (b) Experimental results: Effect of Spindle Speed (rpm) and feed (mm/rev) on Torque(N-m)

5. Conclusion

The purpose of this thesis was to improve the FEM model, to simulate the dynamics and kinematics of a drilling procedure of titanium alloy with a conventional twist drill to examine the effect of the cutting parameters on the drilling thrust force and torque magnitude. The drilling process Ti6Al4V titanium alloy was studied by using the FEM model and tested, and confirmed experimentally. A thermomechanically coupled 3D Finite element model, which includes complex tool geometry, constitutive models suitable for high strain rate, and process parameters, was modeled. A total of 9 simulations are performed to examine the effect of drilling parameters on drilling performance. The model provided a good estimation of thrust force and overestimated the torque. The thrust force increases with the feed. The lower spindle speed results in a higher amount of thrust. Feed rates have a rather greater influence on the thrust force than the spindle speed. The amalgamation of two values, one is a higher feed rate, and another is lower spindle speed, results are the highest amount of thrust. An amalgamation of higher feed rate and Spindle Speed results is the highest amount of torque.

References

- [1] Armarego, E. J. A., and C. Y. Cheng. "Drilling with flat rake face and conventional twist drills—I. theoretical investigation." *International Journal of Machine Tool Design and Research* 12, no. 1 (1972): 17-35. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0020-7357\(72\)90009-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/0020-7357(72)90009-1)

- [2] Armarego, E. J. A., and C. Y. Cheng. "Drilling with flat rake face and conventional twist drills—II. Experimental investigation." *International Journal of Machine Tool Design and Research* 12, no. 1 (1972): 37-54. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0020-7357\(72\)90010-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/0020-7357(72)90010-8)
- [3] Merchant, M. Eugene. "Basic mechanics of the metal-cutting process." (1944): A168-A175. <https://doi.org/10.1115/1.4009380>
- [4] Milton, C. Shaw, and M. Shaw. "Metal cutting principles." ed: Clarendon Press, Oxford Science Publication, UK (1984).
- [5] Chandrasekharan, V., S. G. Kapoor, and R. E. DeVor. "A mechanistic model to predict the cutting force system for arbitrary drill point geometry." (1998): 563-570. <https://doi.org/10.1115/1.2830160>
- [6] Gong, Yongping, and Kornel F. Ehmann. "Mechanistic model for dynamic forces in micro-drilling." In *ASME International Mechanical Engineering Congress and Exposition*, vol. 35494, pp. 19-28. American Society of Mechanical Engineers, 2001. <https://doi.org/10.1115/IMECE2001/MED-23302>
- [7] Strenkowski, J. S., C. C. Hsieh, and A. J. Shih. "An analytical finite element technique for predicting thrust force and torque in drilling." *International Journal of Machine Tools and Manufacture* 44, no. 12-13 (2004): 1413-1421. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijmactools.2004.01.005>
- [8] Yang, Xiaoping, and C. Richard Liu. "Machining titanium and its alloys." *Machining Science and Technology* 3, no. 1 (1999): 107-139. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10940349908945686>
- [9] Ezugwu, E. O., and Z. M. Wang. "Titanium alloys and their machinability—a review." *Journal of materials processing technology* 68, no. 3 (1997): 262-274. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0924-0136\(96\)00030-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0924-0136(96)00030-1)
- [10] Li, Rui, Parag Hegde, and Albert J. Shih. "High-throughput drilling of titanium alloys." *International Journal of Machine Tools and Manufacture* 47, no. 1 (2007): 63-74. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijmactools.2006.02.012>
- [11] Yang, Ji Hong, Shou Jin Sun, Milan Brandt, and Wen Yi Yan. "3D finite element modeling of the machining of Ti6Al4V alloys." In *Advanced Materials Research*, vol. 189, pp. 1926-1929. Trans Tech Publications Ltd, 2011. <https://doi.org/10.4028/www.scientific.net/AMR.189-193.1926>
- [12] Klamecki, Bronislaus Eugene. *INCIPIENT CHIP FORMATION IN METAL CUTTING--A THREE-DIMENSION FINITE-ELEMENT ANALYSIS*. University of Illinois at Urbana-champaign, 1973. <https://www.proquest.com/pagepdf/302651127?accountid=16605>
- [13] Guo, Y. B., and D. A. Dornfeld. "Finite element modeling of burr formation process in drilling 304 stainless steel." *J. Manuf. Sci. Eng.* 122, no. 4 (2000): 612-619. <https://doi.org/10.1115/1.1285885>
- [14] Marusich, T. D., S. Usui, R. Aphale, N. Saini, R. Li, and A. J. Shih. "Three-dimensional finite element modeling of drilling processes." In *International Manufacturing Science and Engineering Conference*, vol. 47624, pp. 471-478. 2006. <https://doi.org/10.1115/MSEC2006-21059>
- [15] Isbilir, Ozden, and Elaheh Ghassemieh. "Finite element analysis of drilling of titanium alloy." *Procedia engineering* 10 (2011): 1877-1882. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.proeng.2011.04.312>
- [16] Gardner, Joel D., and David Dornfeld. "Finite element modeling of drilling using DEFORM." (2006). <https://escholarship.org/uc/item/9xg0g32g>
- [17] Ahmed, Naseer. "Effect of changing drilling parameters on thrust force and torque." *Middle-East Journal of Scientific Research* 21, no. 2 (2014): 347-352. [https://www.idosi.org/mejsr/mejsr21\(2\)14/8.pdf](https://www.idosi.org/mejsr/mejsr21(2)14/8.pdf)
- [18] Bono, Matthew, and Jun Ni. "A model for predicting the heat flow into the workpiece in dry drilling." *J. Manuf. Sci. Eng.* 124, no. 4 (2002): 773-777. <https://doi.org/10.1115/1.1511176>

- [19] Ozcelik, Babur, and Eyup Bagci. "Experimental and numerical studies on the determination of twist drill temperature in dry drilling: A new approach." *Materials & design* 27, no. 10 (2006): 920-927. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matdes.2005.03.008>
- [20] Lee, Woei-Shyan, and Chi-Feng Lin. "High-temperature deformation behaviour of Ti6Al4V alloy evaluated by high strain-rate compression tests." *Journal of Materials Processing Technology* 75, no. 1-3 (1998): 127-136. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0924-0136\(97\)00302-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0924-0136(97)00302-6)

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